

Psychodiagnostic Chart-2 (PDC-2)

The Operationalized PDM-2 - Adult version 8.1 • © 2015 Robert M. Gordon and Robert F. Bornstein

Name: _____ Age: _____ Gender: _____ Ethnicity: _____

Date of Evaluation: ____/____/____ Evaluator: _____

Section I: Level of Personality Organization

Consider your client's mental functions in determining the level of personality organization. Use these four mental functions to efficiently capture the level of personality organization. Rate each mental function on a scale from 1 (Severely impaired) to 10 (Healthy).

1. **Identity:** *ability to view self in complex, stable, and accurate ways* _____
2. **Object Relations:** *ability to maintain intimate, stable, and satisfying relationships* _____
3. **Level of Defenses:** (using the guide below, select a single number) _____
 - 1-2: Psychotic level (delusional projection, psychotic denial, psychotic distortion)
 - 3-5: Borderline level (splitting, projective identification, idealization/devaluation, denial, acting out)
 - 6-8: Neurotic level (repression, reaction formation, intellectualization, displacement, undoing)
 - 9-10: Healthy level (anticipation, self-assertion, sublimation, suppression, altruism, and humor)
4. **Reality Testing:** *ability to appreciate conventional notions of what is realistic* _____

Overall Personality Organization

Considering the ratings and your clinical judgment, circle your client's overall personality organization.

Healthy Personality- characterized by mostly 9-10 scores, life problems rarely get out of hand and enough flexibility to accommodate to challenging realities. (Use "9" for people at the high functioning neurotic level.)

Neurotic Level- characterized by mostly 6-8 scores, basically a good sense of identity, good reality testing, mostly good intimacies, fair resiliency, fair affect tolerance and regulation, rigidity and limited range of defenses and coping mechanisms, favors defenses such as repression, reaction formation, intellectualization, displacement, and undoing. (Use "6" for people who go between borderline and neurotic levels.)

Borderline Level- characterized by mostly 3-5 scores, recurrent relational problems, difficulty with affect tolerance and regulation, poor impulse control, poor sense of identity, poor resiliency, favors defenses such as splitting, projective identification, idealization/devaluation, denial, omnipotent control, and acting out.)

Psychotic Level- characterized by mostly 1-2 scores, delusional thinking, poor reality testing and mood regulation, extreme difficulty functioning in work and relationships favors defenses such as delusional projection, psychotic denial, and psychotic distortion. (Use "3" for people who go between psychotic and borderline levels.)

Section II: Personality Syndromes (P-Axis)

These are relatively stable patterns of thinking, feeling, behaving and relating to others. Normal level personality patterns do not involve impairment, while personality syndromes or disorders involve impairment at the neurotic, borderline, or psychotic

Check off as many personality syndromes as apply from the list below; and then circle the one or two personality styles that are most dominant. Leave blank if none.

(For research purposes, you may also rate the level of severity for all styles, using a 1-5 scale: 1 = Severe Level; 3 = Moderate Severity; and 5 = High Functioning).

	<i>Level of Severity</i>		<i>Level of Severity</i>
<input type="checkbox"/> Depressive Subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introjective • anaclitic • converse manifestation: hypomanic 	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Hysteric-Histrionic Subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inhibited • demonstrative 	_____
<input type="checkbox"/> Dependent Subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • passive-aggressive • converse manifestation: counterdependent 	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Narcissistic Subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • overt • covert • malignant 	_____
<input type="checkbox"/> Anxious/ Avoidant/ Phobic Subtype: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • converse manifestation: counterphobic 	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Paranoid	_____
<input type="checkbox"/> Obsessive-Compulsive	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Psychopathic Subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • passive-parasitic, con-artist • aggressive 	_____
<input type="checkbox"/> Schizoid	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Sadistic	_____
<input type="checkbox"/> Somatizing	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Borderline	_____

Section III: Mental Functioning (M-Axis)

Rate your client's level of strength or weakness on each of the 12 mental functions below, on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 = Severe deficits; 5 = Healthy). Then sum the 12 ratings for a Level of Severity score.

A. Cognitive and affective processes

- 1. Capacity for regulation, attention, and learning _____
- 2. Capacity for affective range, communication, and understanding _____
- 3. Capacity for mentalization and reflective functioning _____

B. Identity and relationships

- 4. Capacity for differentiation and integration (identity) _____
- 5. Capacity for relationships and intimacy _____
- 6. Self-esteem regulation and quality of internal experience _____

C. Defense and coping

- 7. Impulse control and regulation _____
- 8. Defensive functioning _____
- 9. Adaptation, resiliency and strength _____

D. Self-awareness and self-direction

- 10. Self-observing capacities (psychological mindedness) _____
- 11. Capacity to construct and use internal standards and ideals _____
- 12. Meaning and purpose _____

Overall level of personality severity (Sum of 12 mental functions): _____

[Healthy/Optimal Mental Functioning 54-60; Appropriate Mental Functioning with Some Areas of Difficulty 47-53; Mild Impairments in Mental Functioning 40-46; Moderate Impairments in Mental Functioning 33-39; Major Impairments in Mental Functioning 26-32; Significant Defects in Basic Mental Functions 19-25; Major/Severe Defects in Basic Mental Functions 12-18]

Section IV: Symptom Patterns (S-Axis)

List the main PDM symptom patterns (*e.g., those that are related to psychotic disorders, mood disorders, anxiety disorders, event and stress disorders, specific symptom disorders, addiction and medically related disorders, etc.*)

(If required, you may use the DSM or ICD symptoms and codes here.)

Symptom/Concern: _____ Level: _____

Symptom/Concern: _____ Level: _____

Symptom/Concern: _____ Level: _____

Section V: Cultural, Contextual and Other Relevant Considerations
